

Education Quarterly Reviews

Nguyen, H. T., & Nguyen, N. T. (2022). The Influence of Regulations of the Ministry of Finance, Requirements from Related Parties, and the Application of IFRS in Teaching on the Quality of Accounting and Auditing Teaching Staff in Vietnam. *Education Quarterly Reviews*, 5(1), 449-461.

ISSN 2621-5799

DOI: 10.31014/aior.1993.05.01.454

The online version of this article can be found at:
<https://www.asianinstituteofresearch.org/>

Published by:
The Asian Institute of Research

The *Education Quarterly Reviews* is an Open Access publication. It may be read, copied, and distributed free of charge according to the conditions of the Creative Commons Attribution 4.0 International license.

The Asian Institute of Research *Education Quarterly Reviews* is a peer-reviewed International Journal. The journal covers scholarly articles in the fields of education, linguistics, literature, educational theory, research, and methodologies, curriculum, elementary and secondary education, higher education, foreign language education, teaching and learning, teacher education, education of special groups, and other fields of study related to education. As the journal is Open Access, it ensures high visibility and the increase of citations for all research articles published. The *Education Quarterly Reviews* aims to facilitate scholarly work on recent theoretical and practical aspects of education.

ASIAN INSTITUTE OF RESEARCH
Connecting Scholars Worldwide

The Influence of Regulations of the Ministry of Finance, Requirements from Related Parties, and the Application of IFRS in Teaching on the Quality of Accounting and Auditing Teaching Staff in Vietnam

Hong Thu Nguyen¹, Ngoc Tien Nguyen²

¹ Lecturer, Thu Dau Mot University, Binh Duong, Vietnam. Email: thunh@tdmu.edu.vn

² Faculty of Economics and Accounting, Quy Nhon University, Binh Dinh, Vietnam.

Correspondence: Ngoc Tien NGUYEN, Faculty of Economics and Accounting, Quy Nhon University, Binh Dinh, Vietnam. [Postal Address: 170 An Duong Vuong, Quy Nhon City, Binh Dinh Province, 55000, Vietnam]. Email: nguyenngoctien@qnu.edu.vn

Abstract

This study was conducted to verify the direct influential relationship of the factors of the regulations of the Ministry of Finance, the requirements from the related parties, and the application of international financial reporting standards (IFRS) in teaching at universities and colleges with training in accounting and auditing in Vietnam, and the impact of those factors on the quality of accounting and auditing lecturers. The authors conducted a case study at 30 universities and colleges with training in accounting and auditing, and 208 lecturers who are engaged in teaching accounting and auditing in Vietnam. Next, the study employed the structural model analysis method by PLS_SEM software to process and analyze the collected data. Research results show that there is a relationship between regulations of the Ministry of Finance, requirements from related parties, and the application of IFRS in teaching to the quality of lecturers of accounting and auditing at the universities and colleges, with the order of influence from high to low, respectively, (i) Applying IFRS to the training of accounting and auditing majors, (ii) Regulations of Ministry of Finance on the application of IFRS and (iii) Requirements from related parties.

Keywords: Applying IFRS to Teaching, Quality of Teaching Staff, Teaching, Universities and Colleges, Vietnam

1. Introduction

In response to the trend of integration and convergence with international accounting, the Ministry of Finance of Vietnam has issued a roadmap to apply IFRS to enterprises in Vietnam (Ministry of Finance, 2020). Accordingly, as a training place for accounting and auditing human resources for enterprises, the universities and colleges with training in accounting and auditing in Vietnam need to make changes to meet the roadmap of applying IFRS of the Ministry of Finance, in line with the country's international accounting harmonization process in attracting investment and meeting the requirements of related parties.

However, currently in Vietnam, the accounting and auditing training process is still governed by the Law on Accounting, Accounting Standards, and the Enterprise Accounting System of Vietnam. Therefore, when switching to applying IFRS in teaching, it is required that lecturers teaching accounting and auditing professions need to be trained and fostered with knowledge of IFRS, and at the same time, the lecturers themselves are supposed to be eager for learning to develop expertise, understand and apply IFRS principles to teaching to ensure that the process of imparting IFRS knowledge is to the point, with enough principles of applying IFRS and suitable for each target audience.

In addition, to apply IFRS to teaching accounting and auditing professions at universities and colleges in Vietnam, in addition to the difficulties in rebuilding training programs and compiling training materials, investing in facilities and information technology infrastructure related to IFRS, etc, and improving the quality of accounting and auditing teaching staff of the universities and colleges in Vietnam in the current context is really necessary. This is because teachers are considered the most important and valuable learning resources for students; teachers need to have complete knowledge and understanding of the subject they are teaching, to have the necessary skills and teaching experience to effectively convey and exchange such knowledge and understanding to students in the teaching environment and teaching process.

In this study, to evaluate and measure the quality of the teaching staff, the authors used a set of standards on the competency standards of Profession-Oriented Higher Education (POHE2) issued by Vietnam's Ministry of Education and Training (Ministry of Education and Training, 2014). The structure of this research paper consists of five parts, the next part is the literature review, the third part is the research methodology, the fourth part is the research findings, the fifth part is the discussion of the research results, and the sixth part is the conclusion.

2. Literature review

In the field of higher education, the application of IFRS in teaching has been examined in a number of studies, each research depends on different perspectives to make assessments, raise opinions as well as to make various recommendations, typically:

Dow and Feldman (1997) argue that to teach IFRS effectively, it is necessary to teach in small numbers, teach in a case method and focus on specific case handling related to IFRS. Furthermore, it takes time to develop teaching content. Similarly, Hilton and Johnstone (2013) also point to the fact that time constraints prevent them from adding content and real-life situations to their curricula when teaching IFRS. Munter and Reckers (2009) state that developing IFRS-related teaching materials is very difficult, and 72% of the faculty surveyed for the study said that teaching IFRS in the curriculum is very difficult, involving many obstacles. Zhu et al. (2011) show that IFRS standards need to be mentioned more in the curriculum because teachers are increasingly appreciating the convergence between IFRS and US GAAP. Research results show the difficulty that the lecturers have to face when applying IFRS in teaching comes from the fact that IFRS documents are still very limited.

Research by Hodgdon et al. (2011) asserts that when teaching IFRS in the classroom, accounting teachers need to ensure that their students understand the real problem of IFRS, identify IFRS principles and related requirements, consider alternative accounting methods, reach consensus on principles, explain the application of IFRS in practice, etc. This process has promoted the change of teaching methods of the lecturers and enhanced the initiative and activeness of students in the process of approaching IFRS. At the same time, research by Jackling et al. (2013) on the impact of the transition to IFRS in Australia shows that the application of IFRS in teaching has led to changes in curriculum and teaching methods, quality expertise of lecturers at universities. Sharing the same view, Garnett (2011) asserted that when teaching IFRS in the classroom, accounting teachers need to ensure that their students understand the nature of IFRS, identify the principles and requirements IFRS which are relevant, consider alternative accounting methods when recording accounting data to reach consensus on the principles of recording and explaining the application of IFRS in practice. This process has helped to change the teaching methods of lecturers and improve students' initiative and activeness in the process of approaching reality.

Research by Coetzee and Schmulian (2012) suggests that accounting teachers need to change their pedagogical methods in teaching, need to be more creative to be able to convey the contents of IFRS. Accordingly, the study recommends IFRS teaching methods that can include case method, simulation method, case analysis, and group or individual presentation. At the same time, the study also suggests that students need to take more responsibility in the learning process and deal with real-life situations related to IFRS contents. In the same vein, Kalifeh (2017), which looks at changes in accounting curricula for college students in the United States when teaching IFRS, shows that progress has not been spread evenly across different regions in the United States. Kalifeh (2017) also proposes solutions to help improve the quality of accounting training to meet the requirements of international accounting integration. In the same research direction, Nanyan et al. (2019) show that schools applying IFRS in teaching will help students better adapt, increase their learning efficiency in ACCA's global exams at both basic and professional levels.

Besides the advantages, studies around the world have also noted that there are barriers to the teaching of IFRS such as the shortage of appropriately qualified teaching staff (Munter & Reckers, 2009; Zhu et al., 2011); there is no opportunity or means to retrain teaching staff so that they can teach a combination of IFRS and national accounting standards (Glover & Werner, 2015).

In Vietnam, Le (2017) states that to improve the quality of human resource training in the accounting profession at training institutions in the current context of deep integration, one of the most important measures is to foster and train IFRS knowledge for lecturers to fully and professionally teach so that they can approach and pass it on to students. Sharing the same view, Trinh (2019) also believes that the training and skills for accountants at universities need to change; the skills of bookkeeping and tax declaration only play a secondary role, serving the main purpose of accounting tasks. Or research by Phan (2020) shows that universities in Vietnam currently do not have a systematic curriculum on IFRS, and lecturers do not have full access to IFRS knowledge. Therefore, to apply IFRS in teaching, it is urgent to foster IFRS knowledge for lecturers through international professional associations in accounting and auditing.

From the review of the above domestic and foreign studies, the authors believe that: (i) When applying IFRS, all countries have established a roadmap, focusing on bringing IFRS into teaching to meet the needs of supplying human resources for related parties, such as enterprises, employers, etc.; (ii) The application of IFRS and the extent of application of IFRS to teaching in different countries are not uniform. Most of the studies have noted that there are positive effects when applying IFRS in teaching from different angles, including the curriculum, teaching methods, students, lecturers, teaching conditions, etc.; (iii) There are many factors that affect the introduction of IFRS into teaching at universities and colleges in different countries, with both internal and external factors of the universities and colleges; (iv) The quality of the teaching staff plays a key and important role in the process of bringing IFRS into effective teaching at the universities and colleges.

3. Methodology

3.1. Research Design

To carry out this study, the authors followed research steps illustrated through the following diagram:

Figure 1: Research procedure

3.2. Research Hypotheses

Regulations of Ministry of Finance on the application of IFRS (X₂)

Regulations are promulgated by the State to harmonize the rights and responsibilities of each citizen and every organization in the social order, towards the harmonization of the community's interests; these are the principles that define social relationships, shape the behavior of members of society and regulate the functioning of society. Accordingly, Trinh (2019) believes that when the Ministry of Finance promulgates regulations on the application of IFRS, it will be a legal basis for training institutions to transform training programs of accounting and auditing for complying with the regulations; accordingly, lecturers must foster and update their knowledge of IFRS to meet teaching requirements, thereby contributing to improving the quality of accounting and auditing teaching staff. Similarly, there are studies by Tran et al. (2019), Pham (2019).

Hypothesis H1: Regulations on the application of IFRS by the Ministry of Finance affect the quality of teaching staff in accounting and auditing.

Applying IFRS to the training of accounting and auditing (Y)

When the universities and colleges apply IFRS to teaching accounting and auditing professions, lecturers of accounting and auditing are motivated to research, study, and update their knowledge about IFRS by themselves, contributing to improving research capacity and teaching quality. Studies by Trinh (2019), Pham (2019), and Phan (2020) all suggest that when the universities and colleges apply IFRS in teaching, the quality of the teaching staff will be improved through understanding and imparting knowledge about IFRS.

Hypothesis H2: Applying IFRS to the training accounting and auditing influences the quality of accounting and auditing lecturers.

Requirements from related parties (X₉)

Parties are considered to be related if one party can control or exercise significant influence over the other party in making financial and operational decisions. Studies by Freeman (1984), Thomas and Lee (1995), Mitchell et al. (1997), Bourne and Walker (2005), Bruce et al. (2008), Ackermann and Eden (2011) all point out that related parties have the right to propose and request legal and urgent requirements for suppliers of products, goods and service in general and other related issues.

Hypothesis H3: Requirements from related parties influence the quality of accounting and auditing teaching staff.

3.3. Research Model

Based on research hypotheses, the authors proposed a research model that is a multivariable regression model with the dependent variable of the quality of accounting and auditing teaching staff and the three independent variables mentioned in each hypothesis of the study, as follows:

Figure 2: Overview of the research model

From the above-proposed model, the authors put forward the expected research equation as:

$$Z = \alpha + \beta_1 * X_2 + \beta_2 * Y + \beta_3 * X_9 + \varepsilon$$

Where:

α , β_1 , β_2 and β_3 are coefficients

ε : is error

3.4. Variables of the Research Model

To serve the process of compiling questionnaires and collecting the data, the authors use the Likert scale (5 options), the rating levels according to this scale are as follows: 1 – Strongly disagree; 2 – Disagree; 3 – Neutral; 4 – Agree; 5 - Strongly agree. The variables and scales of the research model are determined as follows:

Table 1: Variables and scales employed

Order	Factors	Observed variables	Encryption	Sources
Dependent variable				
1	Quality of teaching staff in accounting and auditing (Z)	The application of IFRS in teaching affects the professional capacity of lecturers.	Z_1	Recommended by the authors based on POHE2; Southeast Asia Teachers Competency Framework (SEA-TCF, 2018), and surveyed experts.
		The application of IFRS in teaching affects the teaching capacity of lecturers	Z_2	
		The application of IFRS in teaching affects the capacity of teachers to develop and guide the use of training programs.	Z_3	
		The application of IFRS in teaching affects the capacity of lecturers to relate to the professional world and professional development capacity.	Z_4	
		The application of IFRS in teaching affects the lecturers' capacity of doing scientific research.	Z_5	
Independent variables				
1	Regulations of Ministry of Finance on the application of IFRS (X_2)	Regulations of the Ministry of Finance on applying IFRS to businesses have prompted universities and colleges in Vietnam to apply IFRS in teaching	X_21	Trinh (2019); Tran et al. (2019);

		Regulations on the roadmap for applying IFRS to businesses are the basis for universities and colleges in Vietnam to determine the timelines for applying IFRS to teaching	X_22	Pham (2019); Phan (2020); Nguyen et al. (2020) and surveyed experts
		Regulations on the roadmap for applying IFRS to businesses are the basis for universities and colleges in Vietnam to orient IFRS-related contents to be taught in modules of training programs of accounting and auditing majors	X_23	
2	Applying IFRS to the training of accounting and auditing majors (Y)	Renovating or updating accounting and auditing training programs.	Y_1	Trinh (2019); Tran et al. (2019); Belyaeva (2019); Fogarty & Jonas (2019); Nanyan et al. (2019); Mkhongi (2020); Seifan (2020); Susan (2020); Braun et al. (2020); Szwarc (2020); López-Díaz (2021); Le et al. (2021); EL-Ariss(2021) and surveyed experts
		Establishing/adding learning outcomes related to IFRS knowledge for accounting and auditing training programs.	Y_2	
		Training/Updating knowledge about IFRS for teaching staff.	Y_3	
		Consulting with stakeholders (employment agencies, alumni, professional associations, etc.) about the contents of IFRS to be taught.	Y_4	
		Collecting/Updating/Standardizing documents (lectures, textbooks, reference books, monographs) related to IFRS for teaching purposes	Y_5	
		Orienting/encouraging trainers to select appropriate teaching methods to convey the contents of IFRS to learners	Y_6	
		Investing in facilities, information technology infrastructure, databases/learning materials to serve teaching/learning for lecturers/students	Y_7	
		Coordinating with professional associations and organizations (such as ACCA, SmartTrain, VAA, VACPA, etc.) to jointly support the process of applying IFRS to teaching.	Y_8	
3	Requirements from related parties (X_9)	Social needs (recruitment agencies, professional associations, etc.) influence the application of IFRS into teaching	X_91	Freeman (1984); Thomas & Lee (1995); Mitchell et al. (1997); Bourne & Walker (2005); Bruce et al. (2008); Ackermann & Eden (2011) and surveyed experts
		Learners' needs for future careers and employment opportunities that influence the application of IFRS into teaching	X_92	
		The comments/feedback of the alumni/student network influence the application of IFRS-related knowledge in teaching	X_93	
		Legislative requirements that affect the application of IFRS into teaching	X_94	

3.5. Sample and Data Collection

To collect data for the study, the authors used a pre-designed survey form based on the variables and scales identified. The final survey form was built based on 3 stages.

Stage 1, Developing a draft survey questionnaire: the authors conducted an overview of domestic and foreign studies related to the research problem to identify research gaps. Next, the research team delivered a drafted survey

questionnaire with survey questions consisting of two parts, specifically: (i) general information about respondents, (ii) survey information.

Stage 2, Expert consultation and experimental investigation to complete the scales, observed variables, etc. to be surveyed: in this stage, the authors conducted direct interviews with experts who are administrators, lecturers at universities and colleges, and experts working in professional organizations with the interviews and consultations of 25 people. At this stage, the research team carried out direct interviews about the survey questionnaires designed in Stage 1 and discussed research ideas with experts and lecturers to consider whether the survey questionnaire is appropriate or not, whether it is necessary to supplement or adjust the observed scales and variables accordingly.

Stage 3, Design of the official survey questionnaire: based on the interview results in Stage 2, the authors synthesized and produced a complete survey questionnaire. To increase the effectiveness, accuracy, and feasibility of the survey questionnaire, the authors conducted a discussion with the experts to continue to record more opinions of the experts to perfect the final survey questionnaire at its best.

At the same time, the process of surveying 30 universities and colleges and 208 accounting lecturers at the institutions was conducted through interviews, direct surveys, and surveys through Google Form.

3.6. Analyzing of Data

From the validly collected survey questionnaires, the authors transferred the data to Excel, coding for variables according to each part of the survey questionnaire. Then, all the data was put into PLS-SEM software. In the process of data processing and analysis, the authors employed a number of analytical and testing tools as follows:

First, the authors evaluated the internal consistency reliability through Composite Reliability (CR) and Cronbach's Alpha coefficient (CA). According to Henseler & Sarstedt (2013), the CR index should reach the threshold of 0.7 or higher, which is suitable for confirmatory research. Many other researchers also agree that a CR index of 0.7 or higher is an appropriate threshold for studies (Hair et al., 2017; Bagozzi et al., 1998). According to Hair et al. (2017), the condition to be accepted for the CA coefficient is that it is supposed to be greater than 0.7. At the same time, according to Devellis (2012), the CA coefficient needs to be 0.7 or more to be acceptable. Therefore, in this study, it is appropriate for the authors to choose a threshold for both coefficients to be 0.7 or more.

Second, the authors evaluated the convergence value through the average variance extracted (AVE). This is to ensure AVE is greater than 0.5. (Chin, 2010; Hair et al., 2014, 2017, 2019).

Third, the authors conducted the discriminant value evaluation. The purpose of this analysis step is to show the distinctiveness of a structure from other structures in the model. The Fornell-Larcker criteria are the first way to assess discriminant value; next is to consider cross-loadings. In this way, discriminability is ensured when the square root of the AVE of each variable must be greater than its correlation coefficient with other variables (Fornell & Larcker, 1981). Recently, Henseler et al. (2015) proposes to evaluate the discriminant value through the HTMT index (Heterotrait-Monotrait ratio). Accordingly, this HTMT index value must be less than 0.9 to ensure the discrimination between the two research variables (Hair et al., 2019).

Fourth, the author tested the research hypotheses: Testing the hypotheses about the direct relationship through the path coefficient β and the p-value of the t-test (student test). Specifically: After PLS-SEM is run, the path coefficient (β) represents the hypothetical relationship between the variables. The path coefficient has an approximate normalized value between -1 and +1. The path coefficient approaching +1 represents a strong positive relationship, and vice versa; the closer to zero the relationship between the two research variables is, the weaker the relationship is. (Hair et al., 2017).

Fifth, the authors employed the Bootstrap 1000 technique. This is to evaluate the significance of the path coefficients. At the 5% level of significance, if the p-value is less than 0.05, it indicates that the effects in the model are all significant and vice versa.

4. Results

4.1. Evaluation of the reliability and convergence value of the scale

The reliability of the scales for all research variables is presented in Table 2. The results show that the Composite Reliability (CR) of the research variables ranges from 0.874 to 0.941 and is higher than the minimum threshold of 0.70. The coefficients of Cronbach's Alpha (CA) of the research variables are also greater than the minimum threshold of 0.70 (ranging from 0.809 to 0.928), proving that the scales have high reliability. In addition, the Average Variance Extracted (AVE) values are all 0.635 or higher, which is higher than the minimum threshold of 0.50. Therefore, it can be concluded that the scales for the research variables are fully convergent.

Table 2: The results of the evaluation of the reliability and convergence value of the scale

Scale	CA	CR	AVE
Regulations of Ministry of Finance on the application of IFRS (X_2)	0.902	0.938	0.835
Applying IFRS to the training accounting and auditing majors (Y)	0.928	0.941	0.665
Requirements from related parties (X_9)	0.809	0.874	0.635

4.2. Evaluation of the scale discriminant value

The authors evaluated the discriminant value of the scales through the criteria of the Fornell-Larcker coefficient and the HTMT coefficient. The results obtained are as follows:

First, about the Fornell-Larcker coefficient

Table 3: The results of the evaluation of discriminant value by Fornell-Larcker's criteria

	X_2	X_9	Y	Z
X_2	0.914			
X_9	0.397	0.795		
Y	0.679	0.461	0.815	
Z	0.461	0.399	0.483	0.865

The results of table 3 show that the square root of the Average Variance Extracted ($\sqrt{AVE}$) (figures located on the diagonal, bold) of the variables are from 0.795 or more and larger than the correlation coefficient of the variables (the corresponding figures not in bold, in the same column of variables). Thus, the scales satisfy Fornell-Larcker criteria to get discriminant value.

Second, about the cross-loading

Table 4 shows that the cross-load coefficient of one observed variable is always greater than all its loading coefficients on the remaining observed variables. Therefore, the measurement model achieves discriminant validity.

Table 4: The results of the evaluation of the discriminant value of the scale by the cross-load coefficient

	X_2	X_9	Y	Z
X_21	0.912	0.342	0.689	0.471
X_22	0.904	0.362	0.578	0.388
X_23	0.926	0.382	0.577	0.393
X_91	0.270	0.782	0.403	0.306
X_92	0.377	0.854	0.383	0.346
X_93	0.344	0.823	0.368	0.372
X_94	0.251	0.712	0.293	0.203
Y_1	0.510	0.344	0.781	0.330
Y_2	0.563	0.378	0.843	0.323
Y_3	0.537	0.454	0.842	0.409
Y_4	0.607	0.426	0.851	0.397
Y_5	0.595	0.419	0.831	0.511
Y_6	0.521	0.284	0.756	0.371
Y_7	0.497	0.365	0.776	0.350
Y_8	0.577	0.313	0.832	0.394
Z_1	0.361	0.282	0.366	0.840
Z_2	0.427	0.326	0.554	0.877
Z_3	0.407	0.369	0.335	0.873
Z_4	0.419	0.409	0.422	0.880
Z_5	0.368	0.310	0.349	0.855

Three, about the HTMT coefficient

The authors continued to evaluate the discriminant value of the scale by using the HTMT coefficient. Table 5 shows that the values of HTMT coefficients range from 0.458 to 0.523, which is less than the threshold of 0.90. With the above analysis results, it is proved that the scale for the variables in the research model has the discriminant value.

Table 5: The results of the evaluation of the discriminant value of the scale by the HTMT coefficient

	X_2	X_9	Y	Z
X_2				
X_9	0.458			
Y	0.733	0.523		
Z	0.499	0.444	0.505	

Thus, the scales for the research variables have reliability, ensure convergent value as well as discriminant value. Therefore, the collected data can be well adopted to test the research hypotheses.

4.3. The results of testing the hypotheses about the relationship of the research model

The results of testing the research model in Table 6 show that all three variables X_2, X_9 and Y have a positive influence on the variable Z (the corresponding p-values are all less than 5%). In which, variable Y has the strongest influence on Z (with $\beta = 0.232$, p-value = 0.021 < 0.05) followed by variable X_2 (with $\beta = 0.224$, p-value = 0.009 < 0.05) and lastly is the variable X_9 (with $\beta = 0.199$, p-value = 0.005 < 0.05).

Table 6: Research model test results

Research variables	Research model	
	β coefficient	p-value
X ₂	0.224	0.009
X ₉	0.199	0.005
Y	0.232	0.021

From the results in Table 6, the regression model of factors affecting the Quality of teaching staff in accounting and auditing can be rewritten as follows:

$$Z = 0.224 * X_2 + 0.199 * X_9 + 0.232 * Y$$

Bootstrap 1.000 Analysis

5. Discussion

From the results of regression analysis, it is shown that the order of factors affecting the quality of accounting and auditing lecturers is (i) Applying IFRS to the training of accounting and auditing majors, (ii) Regulations of Ministry of Finance on the application of IFRS and (iii) Requirements from related parties. The results of this study are quite consistent with the reality at the universities and colleges with training in accounting and auditing in Vietnam, and these findings also have similarities with the research results by the researchers mentioned in the literature review and research hypotheses.

Therefore, according to the results of this study, the authors believe that, in order to apply IFRS to teaching at universities and colleges in Vietnam to meet the regulations on the application of IFRS by the Ministry of Finance and requirements from related parties in recruiting accounting and auditing workers, it is required that schools carry out the following activities:

Firstly, colleges with training in accounting and auditing need to urgently deploy training and refresher courses on IFRS knowledge for lecturers participating in teaching IFRS-related modules, considering collaboration with professional organizations and associations such as ACCA to foster IFRS knowledge for lecturers participating in teaching.

Second, schools need to quickly innovate and update their IFRS knowledge to put into accounting and auditing training programs by integrating IFRS knowledge into accounting modules, such as the modules of principles of accounting, financial accounting, international accounting. In the teaching process, it is possible to integrate and teach parallelly between knowledge of IFRS and knowledge of accounting standards and national accounting regimes so that learners can see the difference between accounting regimes of the country with IFRS.

Third, to unify the content and knowledge related to IFRS when it is put into teaching in the knowledge blocks in the training programs of the schools with training in accounting and auditing nationwide, the Ministry of Education and Training needs to coordinate with the Ministry of Finance to issue the learning outcomes of the training program on IFRS-related knowledge so that the schools can easily identify and apply when updating their training programs. At the same time, the universities and colleges are also expected to invest in their facilities to support teaching, including learning materials, information technology infrastructure, etc. to facilitate the teaching and learning activities regarding IFRS.

Fourth, on the part of the teaching staff, the lecturers must change their views on the teaching method; the teaching method should be turned from the presentation into case handling, to simulate reality and apply the principles of IFRS to handle accounting work at enterprises. Active teaching methods should be favored to improve the effectiveness of IFRS teaching for learners.

6. Conclusion

The results of this study show that the factors of applying IFRS to the training of accounting and auditing majors, regulations of the Ministry of Finance on the application of IFRS, and requirements from related parties influence the quality of accounting and auditing teaching staff. In detail, the application of IFRS in teaching accounting and auditing has had a significant influence on the quality of accounting and auditing teaching staff at universities and colleges in Vietnam. Therefore, to meet the requirements of the Ministry of Finance, related parties, and learners' needs, it is required that the universities and colleges in Vietnam organize training and refresher courses on IFRS knowledge for lecturers, investing in teaching aids and quickly innovating and updating training programs on accounting and auditing so that the training products, i.e. the learners, can meet the requirements from related parties in recruitment such as enterprises, professional organizations in accounting, auditing, etc.

Authorship contribution statement

Hong Thu NGUYEN: Conceptualization and design, design of research methodology and instrument. Ngoc Tien NGUYEN: data acquisition, data analysis and interpretation. Hong Thu NGUYEN and Ngoc Tien NGUYEN: Drafting manuscript, critical revision of manuscript, editing.

References

- Ackermann, F., & Eden, C. (2011). Strategic Management of Stakeholders: Theory and Practice. *Long Range Planning*, 44(3), 179-196. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.lrp.2010.08.001>.
- Bagozzi, R. P., Yi, Y., & Nassen, K. D. (1988). Representation of measurement error in marketing variables: Review of approaches and extension to three-facet designs. *Journal of Econometrics*, 89(1-2), 393 – 421.
- Belyaeva, I. G., Samorodova, E. A., Voron, O. V., & Zakirova, E. S. (2019). Analysis of Innovative Methods' Effectiveness in Teaching Foreign Languages for Special Purposes Used for the Formation of Future Specialists' Professional Competencies. *Educ. Sci*, 9, 171. <https://doi.org/10.3390/educsci9030171>
- Bourne, L. M., & Walker, D. H. (2005). Visualising and mapping stakeholder influence. *Management Decision*, 43, 649-660.
- Braun, R. L., Boldt, M. N., Mauldin, S. & Viosca, C. (2020). Accounting graduates with both online and traditional coursework: impact on hiring decisions. *Accounting Education*, 29 (4), 340-355. <https://doi.org/10.1080/09639284.2020.1788613>
- Bruce, G. C., Edward, F., Crawleyb, G. L., Eric S. R. (2008). Value flow mapping: Using networks to inform stakeholder analysis. *Acta Astronautica*, 62 (2008), 324 – 333.

- Chin, W. W. (2010). How to Write Up and Report PLS Analyses. In: V. E. Vinzi, W. W. Chin, J. Henseler, & H. Wang, Ed. 2010. *Handbook of Partial Least Squares: Concepts, Methods and Applications* Berlin, German: Springer, 655–690.
- Coetzee, S. A. & Schmulian, A. (2012). A critical analysis of the pedagogical approach employed in an introductory course to IFRS. *Accounting Education*, 27 (1), 83-100.
- Devellis, R. (2012). *Scale Development Theory and Applications*. Sage Publications, New York.
- Dow, K. J., & Feldmann, D. A. (1997). Current approaches to teaching intermediate accounting. *Issues in Accounting Education*, 12, 61-75.
- El-Ariss, B., Zanelain, E., Ahmed, W. (2021). Using Videos in Blended E-Learning for a Structural Steel Design Course. *Educ. Sci.* 11, 290. <https://doi.org/10.3390/educsci11060290>
- Fogarty, T. J., & Jonas, G. A. (2019). The Goldilocks Relationship between Exam Completion Sequencing and Performance in Accounting Classes. *Advances in Accounting Education: Teaching and Curriculum Innovations*, 22, 89-107. <https://doi.org/10.1108/S1085-462220190000022005>
- Fornell, C. & Larcker, D. F. (1981). Structural equation models with unobservable variables and measurement error: Algebra and statistics. *Journal of Marketing Research*, 18(3), 382–388.
- Freeman, R. E. (1984). *Strategic Management, A Stakeholder Approach*, Pitman Series in Business and Public Policy. Harpercollins College Div, First edition (January 1, 1984).
- Garnett, R. P. (2011). *The role of the framework in IFRS interpretation*. Presentation to the Joint IAA IFRS Foundation IFRS Teaching Special Interest Session (June 27). Fancourt, George, South Africa
- Glover, H., & Werner, E. M. (2015). Teaching IFRS: Options for Instructors. *In Advances in Accounting Education: Teaching and Curriculum Innovations*, 16, 113-131. <http://dx.doi.org/10.1108/S1085-462220150000016006>
- Hair, J. F., Hult, G. T. M., Ringle, C. M., et al. (2014). *A primer on partial least squares structural equation modeling (PLS-SEM)*. USA: SAGE Publications.
- Hair, J. F., Hult, G. T. M., Ringle, C. M., et al. (2017). *A Primer on Partial Least Squares Structural Equation Modeling (PLS-SEM)*. USA: SAGE Publications.
- Hair, J. F., Risher, J. J., Sarstedt, M., et al. (2019). When to use and how to report the results of PLS-SEM. *European Business Review*, 31(1), 2–24.
- Henseler, J., & Sarstedt, M. (2013). Goodness-of-fit indices for partial least squares path modeling. *Computational Statistics* (28), 565–580.
- Henseler, J., Ringle, C. M. & Sarstedt, M. (2015). A new criterion for assessing discriminant validity in variance-based structural equation modeling. *Journal of the Academy of Marketing Science*, 43(1), 115–135. <https://doi.org/10.1007/s11747-014-0403-8>
- Hilton, S., & Johnstone, N. (2013). The IFRS transition and accounting Education: a Canadian perspective post-transition. *Issues in Accounting Education*, 28(2), 253-261. <http://dx.doi.org/10.2308/iace-50366>
- Hodgdon, C., Susan, B. H., & Donna, L. S. (2011). Framework-based Teaching of IFRS Judgements. *Accounting Education: an international journal*, 20(4), 415–439. <http://doi.10.1080/09639284.2011.589587>
- Jackling, B, De Lange, P. A. & Natoli, R. (2013). Transitioning to IFRS in Australian classrooms: impact on teaching approaches. *Issues in Accounting Education*, 28(2), 263-275. <http://dx.doi.org/10.2308/iace-50358>
- Kalifeh, J. A. (2017). *IFRS in Higher Education: An Exploratory Study*. The University of Southern Mississippi, Honors Teses. 475. Available at: http://aquila.usm.edu/honors_theses/475
- Le, T. A. (2017). Discussing accounting training methods according to international financial reporting standards. *Journal of Dai Nam University*. Available at: <http://dainam.edu.vn/en/tin-tuc/trao-doi-ve-phuong-phap-dao-tao-ke-toan-theo-chuan-muc-bao-cao-tai-chinh-quoc-te>
- Le, T. H. P., Tran, T. C. T., Nguyen, T. L. H., Dao, N. M., Ngo, N. M. Q., Nguyen, N. T. (2021). Determining factors impacting the application of IFRS in teaching: Evidence from Vietnam. *Journal of Accounting*, Online Issue 8 (3), 1-12. <https://doi.org/10.5267/j.ac.2021.11.001>
- López-Díaz, M. T., Peña, M. (2021). Mathematics Training in Engineering Degrees: An Intervention from Teaching Staff to Students. *Mathematic*, 9, 1475. <https://doi.org/10.3390/math9131475>
- Ministry of Education and Training (2014) (POHE2). *Profession-Oriented Higher Education (POHE) in Vietnam (phase 2) under the Ministry of Education and Training of Vietnam*. Project code: NICHE/ VNM-103, 1-11.
- Ministry of Finance (2020). *Decision No. 345/QĐ-BTC on Approval of the project to apply financial reporting standards in Vietnam, issued on March 16, 2020*. Hanoi.
- Mitchell, R. K., Agle, B. R., & Wood, D. J. (1997). Toward a Theory of Stakeholder Identification and Salience: Defining the Principle of Who and What Really Counts. *The Academy of Management Review*, 22(4), 853–886. <https://doi.org/10.2307/259247>
- Mkhongi, F.A., Musakwa, W. (2020). Perspectives of GIS Education in High Schools: An Evaluation of uMgungundlovu District, KwaZulu-Natal, South Africa. *Educ. Sci.* 10, 131. <https://doi.org/10.3390/educsci10050131>
- Munter, P., & Reckers, P. (2009). IFRS and collegiate accounting curricula in the United States: 2008 a survey of the current state of education conducted by KPMG and the Education Committee of the American

- Accounting Association. *Issues in Accounting Education*, 24(2), 131–139. <https://doi.org/10.2308/iace.2009.24.2.131>.
- Nanyan, D., Bai, M., Zhang, H., & Zhang, J. (2019). Approaches to learning IFRS by Chinese accounting students. *Journal of Accounting Education*, Available at: <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.jaccedu.2019.04.002>
- Nguyen, T. L. H., Le, T. H. P., Dao, N. M., & Pham, N. T. (2020). Factors affecting enterprises that apply the International Financial Report Standards (IFRS): A case study in Vietnam. *Journal of Asian Finance, Economics, and Business*, 7(12), 409-422. <https://doi.org/10.13106/jafeb.2020.vol7.no12.409>
- Pham, T. T. M. (2019). Renovating accounting and auditing training at Vietnamese universities in the context of economic integration. *Proceedings of the conference "Accounting in Vietnam - Future and prospects*, 144-148.
- Phan, T. A. D. (2020). Applying IFRS in Vietnam: Difficulties and solutions for accounting training universities. *Journal of Banking Science & Training*, 217, 34-42.
- Seifan, M., Dada, O. D., Berenjian, A. (2020). The Effect of Real and Virtual Construction Field Trips on Students' Perception and Career Aspiration. *Sustainability*, 12, 1200. <https://doi.org/10.3390/su12031200>
- Southeast Asia Teachers Competency Framework (SEA-TCF) (2018). *Published in 2018 by the Teachers' Council of Thailand Bangkok*, Thailand. www.ksp.or.th
- Susan, M., Albring, R., Elder, J. (2020). Research Initiatives in Accounting Education: Managing Academic Programs. *Issues in Accounting Education*, 35 (4), 61–74. doi: <https://doi.org/10.2308/ISSUES-2020-020>
- Szwarc, E., Wikarek, J., Gola, A., Bocewicz, G., Banaszak, Z. (2020). Interactive Planning of Competency-Driven University Teaching Staff Allocation. *Appl. Sci.* 10, 4894. <https://doi.org/10.3390/app10144894>
- Thomas, D., & Lee, E. P. (1995). The Stakeholder Theory of the Corporation: Concepts, Evidence, and Implications. *The Academy of Management Review*, 20(1), 65-91.
- Tran, T., Ha, X., Le, T., & Nguyen, N. (2019), Factors affecting IFRS adoption in listed companies: Evidence from Vietnam. *Management Science Letters*, 9(13), 2169–2180. <https://doi.org/10.5267/j.msl.2019.7.035>.
- Trinh, D. V. (2019). Skills - knowledge that accountants need to be equipped to meet the requirements of accounting innovation in Vietnam. *Proceedings of the Vietnam Accounting Conference - Future and Prospects*, 22-23.
- Zhu, H., Rich, K., Michenzi, A., & Cherubini, J. (2011). User-oriented IFRS education in introductory accounting at U.S. academic institutions: current status and influencing factors. *Issues in Accounting Education*, 26(4), 725-750. <https://doi.org/10.2308/iace-50058>.